

Overlay Journals

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Overlay Journal Infrastructure for Meteorological Sciences (OJIMS)

The OJIMS project is investigating the idea of data publication in the atmospheric sciences. It is creating the required mechanics for overlay journals and examine their long term sustainability. The project will also set up a document repository for the atmospheric sciences. This would preserve a range of documents relevant to atmospheric science including journal papers, technical reports, and images.

The project partners are the Royal Meteorological Society and The National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS). The OJIMS project is funded by NERC and JISC

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/ojims>

The traditional online journal model

Overlay journal model for publishing data

